

A model makerspace for the digital and creative start-up entrepreneurs

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Abstract

Start-ups are essential for the future innovation and economic growth, particularly in developing countries. A dynamic ecosystem, structured programs, tailored training and digital fabrication facilities are the keys to ensure the startups survive in the era of disruptive technologies and the fourth industrial revolution. The platforms that match these requirements are makerspaces and fab labs. In this work, the focus is to explore the role of a makerspace in assisting students' startups in digital and creative industries. The participants were 50 students from various backgrounds that went through the same training programs in a makerspace located in Universiti Teknologi MARA, Malaysia. The training modules were designed to equip the students with 21st century technical and digital skills. The outcome of this work is a model makerspace that is suitable for developing startups in the area of digital and creative industries. It emphasizes the training programs, facilities, equipment, management and support for the focus group. Thus, the model can be utilized by the government and policy-makers in order to assist and enhance the performance of the start-up entrepreneurs that are facing challenges due to the pandemic and the current market demands.

Keywords

makerspace, technopreneurs, industry 4.0, startups, higher-education.

1 Makerspace, hackerspace and fab labs

Makerspaces, hackerspaces and fab labs are community spaces that have similar culture, purpose and programs. These are physical spaces that offer tools for free or low cost for people to gather, create, explore, collaborate, learn and share their ideas and knowledge. Users can experiment their ideas in a welcoming environment without fear of failing. Makerspace is a name for the most general space of its kind that is open for any kind of making activities. The members can represent any group including kids, adults, and entrepreneurs. It can be set up using no tech to high tech tools. The philosophy of Maker Movement emphasizes that a makerspace is not about the tools but rather on the building of the maker's culture and mindset of its community (Dougherty, 2013) (Hatch, 2013).

Makerspaces and hackerspaces already existed a long time ago, however in different types and forms (ALA Magazine, 2013). Hackerspaces can be considered an earlier term for a place where a group of people with the same interest gather to share resources and knowledge to create things focusing more on computing and technology (Baichtal, 2011). The first known hackerspace is the Chaos Communication Club (CCC) founded in Berlin, followed by other popular hackerspaces such as Metalab (2006), TechShop (2006) and Edmonton New Technology Society (2009). However, the term "hacker" gives a negative connotation towards illegal data hacking. On the other hand, the general term "maker" gives a sense of inclusivity in line with the maker movement philosophy. It not only reduces the intimidation, but it gives the feeling of belonging to anyone to be part of the movement. It can't be denied the popularity of terms making and maker was promoted in 2005 by the MAKE: magazine published bimonthly by O'Reilly. The

Maker Media, the company that owned the magazine also started the Maker Faire in 2006, which later became a yearly event in many big cities in the United States. Dale Dougherty, the co-founder of the company purposely used the term “maker” over “hacker” as it is more friendly and associated with one’s personal and social development (Dougherty, 2013). The success of the Maker Movement was shown from the popularity of the Maker Faire being held every year, as well as the increased number of makerspaces all over the world.

Fabrication laboratory (Fab Lab) is a type of makerspace that focuses on product prototyping and small-scale personal fabrication. The most well-known fab lab was established in 2001 in the Center for Bits and Atoms, Massachusetts Institute of Technology (MIT). It has various types of tools and high-tech equipment that allows users to create almost anything. Thus, it is the closest model incubator that supports users pursuing innovation and entrepreneurship. The impact from fab labs has inspired many people that leads to more than 1500 fab labs established under the Fab Lab Network which are located in 90 countries, which are run by the locals (*Fab Lab Network*, 2021).

The support from the United States government to the Maker Movement was peak during the President Obama time. The president himself initiated Nations of Makers, launched the Mayor's Maker Challenge and hosted the White House Maker Faire and National Week of Making in 2014-2015. He called all the federal agencies, educational institutions, private sectors and non-profit organizations to participate in the movement. The agenda was to encourage the science, technology, engineering, and mathematics (STEM) education, provide resources for the maker entrepreneurs and foster the advanced manufacturing in the United States. The encouragement led to the opening of makerspaces in the public libraries, museums, schools and higher education institutions all over the United States. The collaborative efforts among all agencies and well-planned strategy have resulted in great success not only for the Maker Movement but also benefit the United States. The outcome led to (1) more funding, networking opportunities, mentoring and trainings for makers from various federal agencies and private companies such as Etsy, Kickstarter and Indiegogo, (2) increase of students becoming makers due to over 150 colleges and universities, more than 130 libraries, major companies such as Intel, Autodesk, Disney, Lego, 3D System have their own makerspaces, allowing students access to new technologies, tools and mentors (*FACT SHEET: President Obama to Host First-Ever White House Maker Faire*, 2014).

In Malaysia, there are currently three registered fab labs under the Fab Lab Network (*Fab Lab Network*, 2021), however, up to our knowledge, there is no published data on the total number of makerspaces. According to the news articles, there are several active makerspaces, however, their programs and tools/equipment mostly are not freely available for the public (Kaur, 2019) (Yun, 2018). The Malaysian Ministry of Education (MoE) and Malaysian Digital Economy Corporation (MDEC) have made efforts to foster digital making by providing funding and support for Digital Maker Hubs in 24 selected schools. They have planned to increase the number of the same makerspace model to more schools by partnering with the private companies (*MDEC, MOE to Expand Digital Maker Hubs Nationwide by End 2021*, 2021). In addition, there are several public makerspaces located in public and academic libraries supported by the United States Embassy in Malaysia (*American Spaces*, 2018). Most of these makerspaces are focusing on the 21st century digital skills and activities associated with Industry 4.0 technologies such as programming, robotics, Arduino/Raspberry pi, drone and 3D printers. The agenda is in line with the government goals to support STEM education and tackle future challenges in the workforce that require people to have digital skills and be able to work with high tech machines.

2 Makerspace for Entrepreneurship

Makerspaces are the closest solution to the market demand of the fourth industrial revolution. The implementation of the same technology and applications in product development and manufacturing. The revolution of personal and small-scale fabrication is on its way to disrupt the market of mass production (Anderson, 2012; Gershenfeld, 2011).

In addition, many studies have found that the socio-technical environment of a makerspace promotes entrepreneurship by leveraging community-based values of social support, transparency, exploration, and

empowerment. The openness of a shared space, access to social technologies, and community of social support helped members develop entrepreneurial skills and self-efficacy (Bergman & McMullen, 2020)(Hui & Gerber, 2017). Makerspaces are providing new opportunities for entrepreneurial development (Rayna & Striukova, 2021). According to the World Economic Forum, makerspace is not only important for entrepreneurship, but also impacted global challenges (Corcini, 2021).

However, currently in Malaysia, there is no specific makerspace, entrepreneurial training or incubator for students in the field of digital and creative. Therefore, the purpose of this work is to develop a model makerspace that can support student startups in the area of creative and digital industries.

3 Methodology

A survey was conducted to evaluate the user experience and outcome of the training program. The survey participants were 50 university students that went through the 8-12 weeks internship training in MAKERLAB Universiti Teknologi MARA (UiTM) in the year 2018-2021. The study comprised the same number of 25 female and male participants were from various study fields, which were clustered into three main categories: Computer Sciences (48%), Art & Design (36%) and Applied Sciences (16%) (Figure 1 a). There are no students from engineering related fields involved in this study. The participants already completed their training with MAKERLAB UiTM and Figure 1 b indicates the current status of the participants, which mainly are still students (29), 13 of participants are employed by companies, 7 of them are self-employed, and only one still seeking a job.

During the structured training program, they were trained to work with the common high-tech equipment in a makerspace for example 3D printers, laser cutting machines, a virtual reality set and Arduino. Depending on their core domain, they also learned digital skills in 3D design, basic programming and web development. As part of the product development process, they were given project assignments to create products by applying what they had learned and allowed to use any equipment in MAKERLAB UiTM supported by free materials.

Figure 1: Survey's participant demographic of 50 students (25: Female, 25: Male).
(left) Study field and (right) Current employment status of the participants

In this study, the goal is to assess the perception of the participants on the role of MAKERLAB UiTM as an incubator for supporting students' startups particularly for digital and creative industries. Specifically, the questions were designed to evaluate the programs/modules, equipment/tools, facilities, management and support in association with entrepreneurship.

4 Results

4.1 Participants' Satisfaction

Survey results from descriptive analysis indicate a high level of satisfaction occurred among the respondents that went for the training in MAKERLAB UiTM with a mean of 4.74, and they also agree that makerspace is the right place for them to start their digital and creative business (mean = 4.52). Thus, overall satisfaction of the respondents towards MAKERLAB UiTM is considered high as shown in Table 1 below.

Descriptive Statistics (N=50)	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
1. Overall Satisfaction				
What is the level of your satisfaction in general towards MAKERLAB UiTM	4.00	5.00	4.74 07	.44234
In my opinion, MAKERLAB UiTM is the right place where students can start their digital and creative business	3.00	5.00	4.51 85	.66562

Table 1: Overall satisfaction of the participants.

4.2 Program and Modules

Five (5) basic modules were introduced during the training programs, which were design thinking, product marketing, product development, promotion and communication skills. All respondents agree that MAKERLAB UiTM has provided them with a high level of design thinking followed by product development (80%), communication skills (72%), product marketing (56%) and the least skills they learned were product promotion techniques (Figure 2).

In general, Table 2 indicates that the respondents perceived that their training made them become highly creative and innovative (mean = 4.6), as well as that they also had exposure to the product development process (mean=3.7).

In terms of the training and experience, the majority of the respondents (88%) understand the process of becoming an entrepreneur. However only 10% are ready to become entrepreneurs and 2% turn to become entrepreneurs after finishing their training program. Thus, this indicates that the program or modules offered at the MAKERLAB UiTM does not emphasize on the entrepreneurship element as more on product development and creative thinking modules (Figure 3).

Descriptive Statistics (N=50)	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
Program & Modules				
During the internship in MAKERLAB UiTM, I learned the process of product development	1.00	5.00	3.70 37	1.66688
The training during my internship made me becoming more creative and innovative	3.00	5.00	4.61 11	.56357

Table 2: Programs and training modules.

Figure 2: Skills learned during the training program.

Figure 3: Training and experiences toward Entrepreneurship

4.3 Facilities and Equipment/Tools

In general, facilities, equipment and the space were highly rated by the respondent, which were rated more than 4.5. The highest ratings were for facilities and equipment with mean=4.6 (Table 3). Figure 4 indicates the top-ranked equipment is the 3D printer with 100% of the respondents agreeing that it is the most useful tool for them. The second most rated tool for the participants was the Arduino kits (33%) and the least useful equipment for them was the drone (9.3%). The responses are not surprising as all the participants were trained to work with the 3D printer, and used it for product prototyping projects, while the other tools were optional for them depending on the background field and interest.

In terms of weather makerspace able to give them ideas in developing their own product and becoming entrepreneurs, both computers with high specification and software were the most important for them as both were rated 81.5%, followed by a green screen studio (63%) and a conducive working space (53.7%) (Figure 5). The requirement for the computers and software might be surprising as all university students owned a personal laptop/desktop. However, it should be noted that the specification of personal computers is usually not tailored for the 3D design/modelling, rendering high resolution graphics and video editing. More importantly, as entrepreneurs, the correct specification of the hardware allows the software to work successfully so that the products (digital/physical) can be completed in a competitive timeline.

Descriptive Statistics (N=50)	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
Tools & Equipment				
The facilities and equipments in MAKERLAB UiTM are more than my expectation	3.00	5.00	4.6296	.59229
The facilities and equipments in MAKERLAB helped me to develop my own product	3.00	5.00	4.5741	.63251
How do you rate the conduciveness of the working space in MAKERLAB UiTM in helping generating of ideas	3.00	5.00	4.5926	.53265
I believe the facilities provided in MAKERLAB UiTM are able to help me becoming an entrepreneur	3.00	5.00	4.5000	.63691

Table 3: Equipment and tools

Figure 4: Facilities and equipment useful for the respondents' product design & development.

Figure 5: Respondents' selection of facilities/equipment for their product development.

4.4 Management and Support

A makerspace requires a management team and dedicated trainers in order to run a structured training program, manage the resources and maintain the equipment. Respondents were highly rated for managerial support during their training in MAKERLAB UiTM (mean=4.70) (Table 4). Regarding the product development support, the respondents ranked equipment/tools in the top list (mean=1.93), followed by mentoring (mean=2.31), conducive working space (mean=2.70), and raw materials (mean=3.06) (Table 5). However, in terms of helping them to start their journey as an entrepreneur, support either internally (space, facilities, training) or externally (industry, government, community) were rated moderately with mean = 3.87 and 3.74, respectively. In response to the specific items, the respondents stated that they

received enough support in terms of the working space (96.3%), materials (90.7%), and mentoring/supervising (94.4%). The least support they received was funding (18.5%) (Figure 6). They also gained exposure and experience from government agencies (70.4%), private companies (75.9%), as well as community (74.1%). However, the participants did not get much experience working with international agencies (11.1%). Additionally, based on the respondents' opinion, 92.6% indicated that the support from private companies is the most important factor that can improve their ability to become entrepreneurs, compared to other factors such as government agencies, communities and international organizations (38.9-55.6%) (Figure 7).

Descriptive Statistics (N=50)	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
Management and Support				
I am satisfied with the management of the MAKERLAB UiTM	4.00	5.00	4.7037	.46091
During my training, the internal supports (space, facilities, equipments, training modules) from MAKERLAB UiTM helped me to start my own business	1.00	5.00	3.8704	.93256
During my training, the external support (industry , government, community) helped me to start my own business	1.00	5.00	3.7407	1.01285

Table 4: Management & other supports

Descriptive Statistics (N=50)	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation	Ranking
Rank the most support that helped you in product development.					
Equipments	1.00	4.00	1.9259	1.09634	1
Mentoring	1.00	4.00	2.3148	1.04293	2
Free Raw Materials	1.00	4.00	3.0556	.95989	4
Working Space & Facilities	1.00	4.00	2.7037	1.07510	3

Table 5: Respondents' ranking of support from MAKERLAB UiTM for product development.

Figure 6: Support that respondent received during the training.

Figure 7: Respondents' knowledge and experience with other agencies during the training.

Figure 8: Factors that can improve a participant's ability to become an entrepreneur.

5 Discussion & Conclusion

The objective of this study is to analyze and identify the requirements of the makerspace and to propose the best model for potential use at higher institutions and national level.

This paper is based on quantitative methods on 50 respondents, which provided a deeper insight and understanding into the phenomenon under investigation. The studies focus on identifying factors that contribute to the development of digital and creative industry's start-ups. Simple surveys were done in investigating whether the facilities, programs/modules, management and support will contribute to the development of creative and digital-preneurs.

The frequency and the descriptive analysis of the survey results in a convenient sample of 50 respondents found that facilities and equipment/tools particularly, 3D printers, computers with high specification and the right software are the most important contributing factors for them in developing their products. On the other hand, the current modules, internal and external support, and funding provided in the makerspace is insufficient for them to become entrepreneurs. Thus, entrepreneurship modules, more collaboration with the external parties and funding should be emphasized in developing entrepreneurs.

However, the study indicated three main factors for a successful makerspace model: (1) Equipment and facilities that integrated technical and entrepreneurship skills which contribute to new product ideas and entrepreneurial skills; (2) Internal and external supports fostering and supporting enterprise and innovation to create the best environment for growth of businesses to start-up and accelerate smart growth, and (3) the sustainability of incubation and innovation programs for high jobs creation for future demands.

In conclusion, the successful adaptation of the makerspace is depending on the support, facilities and programs leads to high outcomes when reaching a higher stage of economic growth based on the development of the number of start-up with high survival rates, and high added value for innovative products and services, as well as fostering an entrepreneurship environment, and commercializing technology transfer.

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